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A facile strategy to fabricate smart coating with self-healing and self-reporting dual functions

CHEN Shusheng

Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering

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Introduction

Cracks

Corrosion

Coating applications

Dual-functional coating

Robust self-reporting coating

Autonomous self-healing coating

Dual-functional coating

The TPE/PU bulk possess strong blue fluorescence, while no fluorescence could be observed for pure PU.

Dual-functional coating

HDI microcapsule

The outer surface of the microcapsules is deposited by a layer of PUF nanoparticles.

TPE/HDI microcapsule

The cured solid core of TPE/HDI microcapsules possess lots of small particles, which should be the TPE crystals.

Dual-functional coating

From the optical microscope with UV lamp, the results confirm that fluorescent signal can only be observed for broken microcapsule.

1 and 2 were the original and broken HDI microcapsule,
3 and 4 were the original and broken TPE/HDI microcapsule.

Dual-functional coating

Epoxy coating containing microcapsules

Pure EP coating

HDI-EP coating

TPE/HDI-EP coating

White light

UV light

TPE/HDI-EP coating possess self-healing and self-reporting dual

Dual-functional coating

Pure EP coating

HDI EP coating

HDI+TPE EP coating

The SEM images confirm that the cracks were self-repaired by HDI agent.

Dual-functional coating

Fluorescent OM

Pure EP coating

HDI EP coating

HDI+TPE EP coating

From the optical microscope with UV lamp, the results confirm that the broken HDI+TPE MC near the crack exhibit strong fluorescence.

Thank you for your attention!

Q&A